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A STUDY ON THE COMPOSITION METHOD OF VISUAL ILLUSIONS

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ABSTRACT

Composition of pictures is organization and arrangement of shapes and objects. It is a method of visually showing the interrelations between objects. The design of visual illusions is use of the gap in visual experience formed by visual cognition and real situation to display illusions. For understanding organization and arrangement of shapes and objects in visual illusions, composition (an act turning thoughts into pictures) has its significant meaning and value.

This study investigates into the design of visual illusions from the angle of visual psychology, painting and design application, with an aim to devise composition methods of visual illusions and explain how they are designed. The survey in this research is divided into two stages. The first stage was done through literature analysis. Object layout in illusion design was discussed with different sources, and composition methods of visual illusions were also developed in this stage. The second stage contains the method of expert interviews by which we surveyed the relations between illusion category and composition method. We finally have the following results: (1) in the design of visual illusions, four composition methods - separation, adjacency, overlap and transference - are defined with the idea of coordinate axis according to the distance, locations and directionality between objects; (2) a survey of expert interviews shows that among all the 115 visual illusions, "overlap" is the main composition of 25 impossible figures, taking up 22 (88%). In the remaining 90 ambiguity images, 37 of them belong to "separation" (41%), 25 to "adjacency" (27.8%), 11 to "overlap" (12.2%) and 17 to "transference" (18.9%). We have offered definite composition methods of visual illusions for reference of graphic designers as they are creating figures.

Keywords: composition, visual illusion, coordinate axis

INTRODUCTION

Composition of pictures is organization and arrangement of shapes and objects. It is a method of visually showing the interrelations between objects (Pascal Mamassian, 2008). The design of visual illusions is use of the gap in visual experience formed by visual cognition and real situations to display illusions. (E. Bruce Goldstein, 2009; Richard L. Gregory, 1997). Visual illusions have been applied to works of art since the Renaissance in the 16th century; however, the viewer's knowledge of them is usually limited to the appreciation of visual sense of beauty. The research into visual illusion design from a psychological point of view will help understand "how people look at something"; in terms of graphic design, on the other hand, composition (an act turning thoughts into pictures) has its significant meaning and value for understanding organization and arrangement of shapes and objects in visual illusions. This study investigates into the design of visual illusions from the angle of visual psychology, painting and design application, with an aim to devise composition methods of visual illusions and explain how they are designed. The survey in this research is divided into two stages. The first stage was done through literature review and expert interviews. Object layout in illusion design was discussed with different sources, and composition methods of visual illusions were also developed at this stage. The second stage contains the method of expert panel by which we surveyed the relations between illusion category and composition method, and defined the design rules of visual illusions. The research framework is as follows:

Figure 1 The research framework of visual illusion design

LITERATURE REVIEW

DEFINITION

An optical illusion (also called a visual illusion) is characterized by visually perceived images that differ from objective reality. The information gathered by the eye is processed in the brain to give a perception that does not tally with a physical measurement of the stimulus source; a picture or image that tricks your eyes and makes you see something that is not actually there (Wikipedia, 2010; Longman English Dictionary, 2010). In psychology, "illusion" means the perception of outside matters cannot match their objective qualities (E. Bruce Goldstein, 2009; Rita L. Atkinson, Richard C. Atkinson, Edward E. Smith, Ernest R. Hilgard, 1991). The application of visual illusions is available in various fields of design. They are different in connotation according to the purposes of their design. For a graphic designer, visual illusions create camouflage by using clues. The viewer's mistaken reaction to shapes and colors, after he/she sees them, makes matters different from real situations. This contradiction in visual experience may cause emotional reaction, and this is what "visual illusion" means (P.C. Lin, 1996; Naomi Asakura, 1993; C.T. Yang, 1992; Y. F. Chiu, 1990; R. G. Carraher & J.B. Thurston, 1987; Kevin Gatta, Gusti Lange, & Marilyn Lyons, 1991). Therefore, this study defines visual illusions as images that show visual and sensory deviation to create visual tricks by deception, and that guide the viewer's sight and cause expected visual reaction. Such images are considered to bring the viewer novel experience and surprise felt like solving a riddle.

THE CATEGORIES OF VISUAL ILLUSIONS

Psychologist Richard Gregory (1990), from physical, physiological and cognitive aspects, classified visual illusions into three categories: ambiguities,

distortions, paradoxes and fictions, according to their reasons. In the pattern recognition theory, visual illusions can be divided into perceptual hypothesis and perceptual logic according to the ways they are distinguished (Henry Gleitman Gleitman, Henry; Reisberg, Daniel; Gross, James, 2007). In the field of graphic design, Tom Himpe & Will Collin (2008) proposed that the content of ads in visual illusion can be divided into false copies, false perspectives and false perceptions, according to the manifestations of visual design. Robin Landa (2001) regarded visual illusions as one of the ways to show creativity. He put forward the following techniques of visual illusions: (1) real/unreal, (2) geometric illusion, (3) impossible space and (4) depth perception. J. H. Chen and T. M. Yang (1998) classified visual illusions into geometric illusions and ambiguous figures; C.T. Yang (1997) classified them into geometric illusions, figure-ground reverse, ambiguous figures and contradictory figures; Naomi Asakura (1993) classified them into reverse pictures and irrational figures; Shiroseki (2008) classified them into double illusions and reverse illusions. Based on perceptive cognition and practical application, we have summarized the above literature reviews and accordingly divided visual illusions into two categories: (1) ambiguity images and (2) impossible figures.

Ambiguity Images

With a purpose of visual communication, the images have two or more meanings at one time (see Figure 2) or have a reverse effect as the viewer have different viewing points, such as far-near reverse (Figure 3) and figure-ground reverse (Figure 4) (Henry Gleitman Gleitman, Henry; Reisberg, Daniel; Gross, James, 2007; C.T. Yang, 1992).

Fig. 2 Ambiguous figure

Fig. 3 Far-near reverse

Fig. 4 Figure-ground reverse

Impossible Figures

Refer to the ones that do not exist in real life.

Although a picture on a two-dimensional plane may

look cubic, it is unlikely to become a real solid in three-dimensional space. The contradictory figure with a crossing (Figure 5), that with a difference in the focus (Figure 6) and spatially-irrational figure (Figure 7) are good examples (Henry Gleitman of space, Henry; Reisberg, Daniel; Gross, James, 2007; Bruno Ernst, 1986).

Fig. 5 Contradictory figure with a crossing

Fig. 6 contradictory figure with a difference in the focus

Fig. 7 Spatially-irrational figure

RESEARCH METHOD

The research is divided into two stages. Composition methods of visual illusions were developed at the first stage. Object layout in illusion design was discussed with different sources. The second stage contains the method of expert interviews by which we surveyed the relations between illusion categories and composition methods.

SURVEY 1: DEVELOPING COMPOSITION METHODS OF VISUAL ILLUSIONS

The survey was conducted through literature review and expert interviews. Object layout in illusion design was discussed with different sources, and composition methods of visual illusions were also developed at this stage.

Test samples

The samples were sourced from a series of books by Al Seckel, an American authority on visual and sensory illusions: *The Art of Optical Illusions* (2000), *Great Book of Optical Illusions* (2004) and *Masters of Deception* (2004). Non-picture geometrical illusions, photographic and repeated ones were deleted from the list. We finally obtained 115 samples, edited them using Photoshop and sized them 12X15cm in length and width of grey picture cards.

Steps of the survey

This study defines visual illusions from the angle of visual psychology (E. Bruce Goldstein, 2009 ; Richard L. Gregory, 1997), painting and design application. Composition methods with the concept of coordinates were developed by the idea of layout grid (Kimberly Elam, 2004), proportion in geometry (Kimberly Elam, 2001), drawing (Greg Albert, 2003) and the relationship between objects in graphic design (S. Tanaka, J. Kurumizawa, S. Inokuchi, Y. Iwadate, 2000).

SURVEY 2: THE RELATIONS BETWEEN ILLUSION CATEGORIES AND COMPOSITION METHODS

Test samples

115 visual illusions – the same as the samples in survey 1.

Survey participants

Four expert members with graphic design and design education background were invited to join the survey.

Steps of the survey

In the survey that used the method of expert interviews, four expert members with graphic design and design education background were invited to judge the 115 samples collected by the researcher according to the composition methods of visual illusions defined in this research. The composition method of a visual illusion is classified in the following table.

Table 1 The classification of a visual illusion by composition method

No.	Visual Illusion	Objects' Positions	Composition Method	Category
056		Separation	Ambiguity Image	

RESULTS

We use graphic composition principles to analyze the composition objects in visual illusions. We have also investigated into composition methods according to

the distance, locations and directionality between objects and their interrelations in planar space.

THE COMPOSITION METHODS OF VISUAL ILLUSIONS

Based on the distance, locations and directionality between an object and its adjoining objects, we propose the idea of coordinate axis as a tool for measuring composition method, because a coordinate axis can represent location, distance and 3-dimension space.

Fig. 8 The development of coordinate axes

With the idea of coordinate axis, we have proposed four composition methods - separation, adjacency, overlap and transference - according to the distance, locations and directionality between objects and their interrelations in planar space. They are described as follows:

Separation

When some objects compose a whole image, every main object does not mix or touch its adjoining objects in the contour, meaning that the objects may keep their original shapes and there exists space between objects. In Figure 9, the visual image is composed of ships (A, B, C, D), human faces (E, F), islands and totems, altogether judged to be a human head by perceptual experience.

Fig. 9 Separation(Source: optical illusion, AI Seckel, 2004)

Adjacency

When two or more different or identical objects compose a whole image, the objects are adjacent to each other with shared contour but without overlap, meaning that the objects may keep their original shapes and there exists no space between objects. In Figure 10, the visual illusion is composed of women legs (A) and men legs (B). The women legs are adjacent to men legs, with shared contour but without overlap.

Fig. 10 Adjacency(Source: optical illusion, AI Seckel, 2004)

Overlap

In a picture, two or more complete images can be recognized. When we overlap the images (Figure 11), there will be a joining part of them; when we cover one image with the other (Figure 12), part of the shape will be covered, but the two images have common shaping elements.

Fig. 11 Two or more images overlap (Source: optical illusion, AI Seckel, 2004)

Fig. 12 One image covered by the other(Source: optical illusion, AI Seckel, 2004)

In Figure 13, the whole image shows both a young girl and an old lady. If taking route A->B->C->D, we can see a young girl (Fig. 13a); If taking A->B->C->E, we see an old lady (Fig. 13b). The two images have common objects - hair and hat.

Fig. 13a Adjacency Fig. 13b Adjacency (Source of the materials: optical illusion, Al Seckel, 2004)

Transference

In such an image, the original shape stays unchanged, but the positions and angles of the objects are altered. Such changes include displacement and switch of positions, change in angle and its rotation. In Figure 14a, the portrait is wearing a helmet (A), with lifted eye corners (B) and drooping mouth corners (C); after a rotation for 180°, it becomes the image in Figure 14b: the helmet (A) turns into a navy cap (C''), lifted eye corners (B) into contempt in the eye (B'') and drooping mouth corners (C) into surprised expression (A'').

Fig. 14a Transference 14b Transference (Source of the materials: optical illusion, Al Seckel, 2004)

THE RELATIONS BETWEEN ILLUSION CATEGORIES AND COMPOSITION METHODS

The composition methods of visual illusions are judged according to the shared opinions of the four expert members. The four composition methods mentioned above are all applied to the 115 samples. Among them, 38 belong to "separation" (33%), 27 to "adjacency" (23.5%), 33 to "overlap" (28.7%) and 17 to "transference" (14.8%). A cross comparison between illusion categories and composition methods shows that "overlap" is the main composition of 25 impossible figures, taking up 22 (88%). In the remaining 90 ambiguity images, 37 of them belong to "separation" (41%), 25 to "adjacency" (27.8%), 11 to "overlap" (12.2%) and 17 to "transference" (18.9%) (see Table 2). This result proves the four composition methods can be rationally operated.

Table 2 The relations between illusion categories and composition methods

Illusion Categories	Composition Methods				Total
	Separation	Adjacency	Overlap	Transference	
Impossible Figure					
(Quantity)	1	2	22	-	25
Ambiguity Image					
(Quantity)	37	25	11	17	90
Total	38	27	33	17	115
Percentage (%)	33%	23.5%	28.7%	14.8%	100%

CONCLUSION

Besides the aesthetic function, visual illusions are planned and purposive. Through intentional design and arrangement of composition, the viewer's processing efficiency of information can be promoted. For a practical designer, a clear set of design method will help to improve the effect of design. This study has defined definite rules of design and proposed four composition methods - separation, adjacency, overlap and transference - for the design of visual illusions with the idea of coordinate axis according to the distance, locations and directionality between objects. From the angle of practical design, We wish to use the composition methods for reference of graphic designers as they are teaching design and creating figures.

Studies of later days are suggested to analyze the relations between viewer cognition and preference caused by the study of various visual illusions. This will provide a basis for the designer to follow and help rectify the errors the designer may make when designing by intuition.

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